

Coiled Hold-Release Mechanism Based on Shape Memory Polymer Composites for Aerospace Applications

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- ✓ Smart material/structure is a new type of material/structure which can sense the change of external environments and respond actively

Shape Memory Polymers (SMP) are polymeric smart materials that have **the ability to recover from temporary shape to their permanent shape** induced by an external stimulus, such as temperature change.

- Shape memory property;
- Variable stiffness,
- Elastic modulus change 200 times

Leng JS, Lan X, Liu YJ, Du SY. *Progress in Materials Science*, 56, 1077-1135 (2011)

Wang WX, Liu YJ, Leng JS. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 320, 38-52 (2016)

Liu TZ, Zhou TY, Yao YT, Zhang FH, Liu LW, Liu YJ, and Leng JS. *Composites Part A*, 100, 20-30 (2017).

— Post micro-buckling mechanics of SMPC under flexure deformation

- The local **post-buckling mechanics** of unidirectional fiber-reinforced SMPC were investigated, and the problem of **small strains and large deformation** was considered.
- The analytical expressions of the **critical buckling curvature, buckling fiber wavelength and buckling fiber amplitude** were determined by the minimum energy principle.
- Based on the buckling deformation of fiber, the small material strain of fiber was used to produce **large geometric deformation of the composite structure**.

Micro-buckling configuration

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} +\infty & (k < k_c) \\ \left[\frac{8\pi^3 v_f E_f I_f (z_{ns}^2 - \frac{4M^2}{k^2})}{v_m G_m d^2 \ln\left(\frac{kz_{ns}}{2M}\right)} \right]^{1/4} & (k \geq k_c) \end{cases}$$

Micro-buckling wavelength at different curvature

Curvature k (m^{-1})	Neutral surface Z_{ns}/t	Half wavelength λ (mm)	
Design value	Theoretical value	Theoretical value	Experimental value
20	0.936	1.45	1.24 ± 0.05
50	0.959	1.41	1.39 ± 0.11
100	0.971	1.42	—

Deployable Structures in Aerospace

- Release device for CubeSat's deployable solar panels
- Latching force are adjustable through interference and thickness
- Featured in light-weight, small-shock and reusable

Schematics of the ultra-light release device

Latching force

Deployment on a prototype

Deployable Structures in Aerospace

- Synchronisation of the deployment of symmetrical structures
- Damage evolution with temperatures
- Preliminary validation on a prototype with a less than 67 ms synchronisation

Deployable Structures in Aerospace

- World's first application of SMPC in Mar exploration
- Dynamic demonstration of flag in deep space
- Deployment adaptability to voltage and ambient temperature

Self deployable mechanism for national flag

Deployment in a simulated Martian environment

Deployable Structures in Aerospace

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Mars probe landing

Dynamic deployment process

On-Mars deployment

Thank you!

